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Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR
SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF LEVOFLOXACIN AND
AZITHROMYCIN BY RP-HPLC IN TABLET DOSAGE
FORM****V. Sri Teja Reddy, Ajay Kumar**Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Narasaraopet Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Narasaraopet, Guntur, Andra Pradesh**Abstract:**

New method was established for simultaneous estimation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin by using Inertsil C18 (4.6mm ×250mm, 5µm particle size), flow rate was 1.0 ml/min, mobile phase ratio was (55:45% v/v) Methanol: Phosphate buffer pH 4.8 (pH was adjusted with ortho phosphoric acid), detection wavelength was 282nm. The instrument used was WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA detector. The retention times were found to be 1.688mins and 3.282mins. The % purity of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin was found to be 99.86%. The system suitability parameters for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 7586, 1.69 and 6235 and 1.58, the resolution was found to be 10.85. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin was found in concentration range of 100µg-500µg and 30µg-70µg and correlation coefficient (r²) was found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % recovery was found to be 100.112% and 100.16%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.1702 and 0.043 respectively. The precision study was precise, robust, and repeatable. The LOD value was found to be 2.1µg/ml and 1.28µg/ml, and LOQ value was 6.3µg/ml and 3.84µg/ml for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin respectively. The results of study showed that the proposed RP-HPLC method is a simple, accurate, precise, rugged, robust, fast and reproducible, which may be useful for the routine estimation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in pharmaceutical dosage form.

Keywords: Levofloxacin, Azithromycin, RP-HPLC, Simultaneous estimation.**Corresponding author:****V. Sri Teja Reddy,**Department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis
Narasaraopet Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
narasaraopet ,Guntur
Andra PradeshE-mail: sritejavanga30298@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION:

Azithromycin should be used only to treat or prevent infections that are proven or strongly suspected to be caused by susceptible bacteria in order to prevent the development antimicrobial resistance and maintain the efficacy of azithromycin. In order to replicate, bacteria require a specific process of protein synthesis, enabled by ribosomal proteins. Azithromycin binds to the 23S rRNA of the bacterial 50S ribosomal subunit. It stops bacterial protein synthesis by inhibiting the transpeptidation/translocation step of protein synthesis and by inhibiting the assembly of the 50S ribosomal subunit. This results in the control of various bacterial infections, Label. The strong affinity of macrolides, including azithromycin, for bacterial ribosomes, is consistent with their broad-spectrum antibacterial activities.¹⁻³ IUPAC name 4-(dimethylamino)-3-hydroxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxy}-2-ethyl-3,4,10-trihydroxy-13-[[[(2R,4R,5S,6S)-5-hydroxy-4-methoxy-4,6-dimethyloxan-2-yl]oxy]-3,5,6,8,10,12,14-heptamethyl-1-oxa-6-azacyclopentadecan-15-one. Molecular weight is 748.9. Molecular formula is C₃₈H₇₂N₂O₁₂.

Figure 1: Structure of Azithromycin

Levofloxacin is a fluoroquinolone antibiotic used to treat infections caused by susceptible bacteria of the upper respiratory tract, skin and skin structures, urinary tract, and prostate, as well as for post-exposure treatment of inhaled anthrax and the plague. In oral and intravenous formulations, levofloxacin is indicated in adults for the treatment of various infections caused by susceptible bacteria, including infections of the upper respiratory tract, lower respiratory tract, skin, skin structures, urinary tract, and prostate. The oral formulation is also indicated in both adults and children 6 months of age and older for the post-exposure management of inhalational anthrax caused by *Bacillus anthracis* and for the treatment and/or prophylaxis of plague caused by

Yersinia pestis.^{4,6} IUPAC name 2-[3,5-bis(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]-N,2-dimethyl-N-[4-(2-methylphenyl)-6-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)pyridin-3-yl]propanamide. Molecular weight is 361.3g/mole. Molecular formula is C₁₈H₀FN₃O.

Figure 2: Structure of Levofloxacin

The literature survey revealed that There are very few methods reported in the literature for analysis of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin alone or in combination with other drugs in the pure form and pharmaceutical formulations by HPLC.⁷⁻¹² In view of the need for a suitable, cost-effective RP-HPLC method for routine analysis of Simultaneous estimation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form, attempts were made to develop simple, precise, accurate and cost-effective analytical method for the estimation of Tamsulosin and Dutasteride. The proposed method will be validated as per ICH guidelines. The objective of the proposed work is to develop a new, simple, sensitive, accurate and economical analytical method and validation for the Simultaneous estimation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form by using RP-HPLC. To validate the developed method in accordance with ICH guidelines for the intended analytical application i.e., to apply the proposed method for analysis of the drug in its dosage form. To apply the developed method for the simultaneous estimation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in Tablet dosage form.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and Reagents: Levofloxacin and Azithromycin were obtained from Aurobindo, Hyderabad. NaH₂PO₄ was analytical grade supplied by Finerchem limited, Orthophosphoric acid (Merck), and Water and Methanol for HPLC (Lichrosolv (Merck).

Equipment and Chromatographic Conditions: The chromatography was performed on a Waters

2695 HPLC system, equipped with an auto sampler, UV detector and Empower 2 software. Analysis was carried out at 282 nm with column Phosphate Buffer (pH-4.8): Methanol (55:45% v/v), dimensions at 35°C temperature. The optimized mobile phase consists of. Flow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min and run time for 6 min.

Preparation of solutions:

Preparation of mobile phase: Accurately measured 500 ml (50%) of HPLC Methanol and 350 ml of Acetonitrile (35%) and 150 ml of Water (15%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filter.

Diluent Preparation:

Accurately measured 450 ml (45%) of HPLC Methanol and 550 ml of Phosphate Buffer (55%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultra sonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filter.

Preparation of the Levofloxacin and Azithromycin standard solution:**Preparation of standard solution: (Levofloxacin)**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Levofloxacin, working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the diluent.

Preparation of standard solution: (Azithromycin)

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Azithromycin working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the diluent. Further pipette 3ml of Levofloxacin, 0.5ml of Azithromycin from stock solutions in to a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Take average weight of Tablet and crush in a mortar by using pestle and weight 10 mg equivalent weight of Levofloxacin, Azithromycin sample into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 7ml of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Procedure:

Further pipette 1.2ml of Levofloxacin, Azithromycin from above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

METHOD:

The developed chromatographic method was validated for system suitability, linearity accuracy, precision, ruggedness and robustness as per ICH guidelines.

System suitability parameters: To evaluate system suitability parameters such as retention time, tailing factor and USP theoretical plate count, the mobile phase was allowed to flow through the column at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min for 6 minutes to equilibrate the column at ambient temperature. Chromatographic separation was achieved by injecting a volume of 20 µL of standard into Inertsil ODS C 18 column (4.6 x 250mm, 5µm), the mobile phase of composition Phosphate Buffer (pH-4.8): Methanol (55:45% v/v) was allowed to flow through the column at a flow rate of 1.0 ml per minute. Retention time, tailing factor and USP theoretical plate count of the developed method are shown in table 1.

Assay of pharmaceutical formulation: The proposed validated method was successfully applied to determine Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in their pharmaceutical dosage form. The result obtained for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin was comparable with the corresponding labeled amounts and they were shown in Table-2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Figure 3: Standard chromatogram

Figure 4: Sample chromatogram

Figure 5: Blank chromatogram

Table 1: System suitability parameters

Parameters	Levofloxacin	Azithromycin
Retention time	1.688	3.282
USP Plate count	7586	6235
USP Tailing	1.69	1.58

Table 2: Assay results for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin

	Label Claim (mg)	% Assay
Levofloxacin	80	99.86
Azithromycin	20	99.86

Linearity: The linearity study was performed for the concentration of 100ppm to 500ppm and 30 ppm to 70 ppm level. Each level was injected into chromatographic system. The area of each level was used for calculation of correlation coefficient. Inject each level into the chromatographic system and measure the peak area. Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient. The results are shown in table 3.

Table 3: Linearity results for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin

Levofloxacin		Azithromycin	
Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Area	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Area
100	585985	30	268764
200	1182468	40	356958
300	1768785	50	445631
400	2326852	60	535186
500	2856874	70	624698
Correlation coefficient	0.999	Correlation coefficient	0.999

Figure 4: Linearity graph for Levofloxacin

Figure 5: Linearity graph for Azithromycin

Accuracy studies: The accuracy was determined by help of recovery study. The recovery method carried out at three level 50%, 100%, 150%. Inject the standard solutions into chromatographic system. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values. The results are shown in table 4.5.

Table 4: Showing accuracy results for Levofloxacin

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Average Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	879537	150	150.048	100.032	100.112%
100%	1743252	300	300.521	100.172	
150%	2609693	450	450.598	100.132	

Table 5: Showing accuracy results for Azithromycin

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Average Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	224271	25	25.114	100.456%	100.16%
100%	445748.3	50	49.952	99.904%	
150%	670006.3	75	75.101	100.134%	

Precision Studies: precision was calculated from Coefficient of variance for six replicate injections of the standard. The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six Injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found. The results are shown in table 6.

Table 6: Precision results for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin

S. No	Levofloxacin	Azithromycin
1	1658254	426598
2	1658952	426589
3	1654857	426985
4	1659854	426587
5	1653298	426515
Mean	1657043	426654.8
Std.dev	2820.29	187.5692
%RSD	0.1702	0.043963

Ruggedness: To evaluate the intermediate precision of the method, Precision was performed on different day. The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found. The results are shown in table 7 and 8.

Table 7: Intermediate precision results for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin on day 1:

S. No	Sample Area 1	Sample Area 2
1	1665985	436598
2	1662598	436855
3	1668484	436598
4	1664598	436587
5	1663579	436741
6	1664587	432659
Mean	1664972	436006.3
Std. Dev.	2060.327	1643.285
% RSD	0.123745	0.376895

Table 8: Intermediate precision results for Levofloxacin and Azithromycin on day 2:

Injection	Area for Levofloxacin	Area for Azithromycin
Injection-1	1648598	415985
Injection-2	1642587	415267
Injection-3	1649852	415986
Injection-4	1648754	415265
Injection-5	1645289	415874
Injection-6	1647581	415632
Average	1647110	415668.2
STD Deviation	2699.291	337.2106
%RSD	0.16388	0.081125

Robustness: As part of the Robustness, deliberate change in the Flow rate, Mobile Phase composition, Temperature Variation was made to evaluate the impact on the method. The flow rate was varied at 0.9 ml/min to 1.1ml/min. The Wavelength varied from 243nm to 247nm. The results are shown in table 9,10,11,12

Robustness results for Levofloxacin

Table 9: Organic Composition results for Levofloxacin:

Flow Rate (ml/min)		System suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
Less Flow rate	0.8	7365	1.62	1.868
Actual Flow rate	1	7586	1.69	1.688
More Flow rate	1.2	7254	1.61	1.544

Table 10: Wavelength variation results for Levofloxacin:

Flow Rate (ml/min)		System suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
Less Flow rate	0.8	6284	1.51	3.621
Actual Flow rate	1	6235	1.58	3.282
More Flow rate	1.2	6168	1.56	2.998

Robustness results for Azithromycin

Table 11: Flow variation results for Azithromycin:

Flow Rate (ml/min)		System suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
Less Flow rate	0.8	6284	1.51	3.621
Actual Flow rate	1	6235	1.58	3.282
More Flow rate	1.2	6168	1.56	2.998

Table 12: Organic Composition results for Azithromycin:

Organic phase		System suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
Less organic phase	50:50	6182	1.54	3.621
Actual organic phase	55:45	6235	1.58	3.282
More organic phase	60:40	6322	1.56	2.302

LOD and LOQ: The sensitivity of RP-HPLC was determined from LOD and LOQ. Which were calculated from the calibration curve using the following equations as per ICH guidelines. The results are shown in table 13.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3\sigma/S \text{ and}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma/S, \text{ where}$$

σ = Standard deviation of y intercept of regression line,

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Table 13: LOD, LOQ of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin

Drug	LOD	LOQ
Levofloxacin	2.10	6.30
Azithromycin	1.28	3.84

CONCLUSION:

The proposed HPLC method was found to be simple, precise, accurate and sensitive for the simultaneous estimation of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in tablet forms. Hence, this method can easily and conveniently adopt for routine quality control analysis of Levofloxacin and Azithromycin in tablet dosage forms.

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